

THE CHALLENGES OF GRAMMATICAL TRANSFORMATION IN TRANSLATION

Ismoilova Gulshoda Turaboy kizi – 2nd course student

Master's departmentnUzbek state world languages university

Annotation. The lesson presents a contemporary understanding of the primary issues with translation and the field of translation studies. papers on translation theory in the sciences. Based on the factual material translation process, methods for completing certain translation jobs are presented, highlighting lexical-semantic, grammatical, and stylistic issues. Examples are utilized as reference points for the English to Uzbek-translations.

Keywords: Grammatical transformations, qualified translation, lexical content, semantic structure, expressive and stylistic function, category of certainty/uncertainty, complex infinitive constructions.

Introduction. Sentences that alter in structure when being translated from English into Uzbek typically do so for lexical reasons. However, the burden of communication frequently necessitates careful consideration of both the word and its grammatical structure. Grammatical transformations include changing a sentence's structure during translation to conform to the rules of the destination language. Depending on whether the structure changes completely or only partially, the transformation might be either full or partial¹. Replacing merely minor elements results in a partial modification of the proposition, whereas replacing the main members of the statement results in its total alteration. When the translator has previously understood the foreign sentence and can therefore see its grammatical structure, professional, qualified translation can start.

Whether it is a continuous understanding or an unauthorized translation is irrelevant. The syntactic structures of English and Uzbek frequently allow for a literal translation, but occasionally, as a result of a variety of factors, the translator is forced to use grammatical transformations, which include full or partial sentence transformation, the substitution of parts of speech and sentence constituents in translation. Even when the structure is comparable in Uzbek, change is frequently required. In the process of translating, the grammatical form and syntactic structure are not considered in isolation from their lexical content. However, the multiplicity of grammatical options enables us to draw attention to them separately. When translating,

¹ Arnold I.V. Fundamentals of linguistic research: Textbook. - M.: Higher School., 1991.

the writing style of someone with a strong personality might be challenging. When an extra function, such as expressive or semantic, is added, a problem results².

When utilizing grammatical transformations, the following things should be taken into account:

- 1) the syntactic function of the sentence;
- 2) its lexical content;
- 3) its semantic structure;
- 4) the context (environment) of the proposal;
- 5) its expressive and stylistic function.

Expressions are constructed differently in lexical and grammatical elements. Values that are lexical in one language that is, articulated through vocabulary can be stated grammatically in other languages. The substitution of English nouns with Uzbek verbs should be considered the most prevalent method of grammatical transformation in translation. These phenomena are linked to the Uzbek language's expansive and adaptable verbal structure. For example, *Drowning is the biggest killer of children in 21 countries, according to a World Health report published in Geneva yesterday.* - *Kecha Jenevada chop etilgan Jahon sog'liqni saqlash hisobotiga ko'ra, cho'kish 21 mamlakatda bolalarning eng katta qotilidir.*

Since the verb *cho'kmoq* cannot be transformed into a verbal noun, its replacement during translation is unavoidable. can use the personal form of the verb *cho'kmoq*, but the participle is undoubtedly the better choice. English nouns are replaced with Uzbek verb forms since the nominative beginning is so prevalent in English. In this case, it is natural to use the English verbal noun typically with the -er suffix in place of the Uzbek verb's form³: *Oh, I'm no dancer* - *Oh, men raqqosa emasman.*

Adjectives from the English language can be changed to nouns, verbs, and adverbs when translated into Uzbek. Consequently, adjectives used to describe white schools and white churches were changed to nouns in the translation of American realities: *oq tanlilar uchun maktablar, oq tanlilar uchun cherkovlar*. Less frequently, a verb must be used in place of an adjective: *As to Balzac, his manners were deplorable* - *Balzakga kelsak, uning xulq-atvori juda achinarli edi*. Adverbs are most frequently used in translation to substitute adjectives. This change is related to the process known as the transfer of epithets, which is widespread in the English language: *Lord Nesby stretched a careless hand* - *Lord Nesbi beparvo qo'lini uzatdi. The accusation has been*

² Kazakova T.A. Translation techniques. - St. Petersburg: Union, 2004.

³ Gafurov I., Muminov O., Qambarov N., Translation theory. - T., 2012.

disproved editorially - Ayblov tahririyat tomonidan rad etilgan. due to the fact that the grammatical phenomena of one language are not present in another, there are grammatical alterations when translating from English into Uzbek:

A rigid sentence structure with predetermined word order is present in English, whereas word order is free in Uzbek; a category of certainty and uncertainty is presented in English; a gerund is a distinctive feature of the English language; complex infinitive constructions (complex subject); perfect and imperfect forms of time in the English tense verb system; and a system of noun cases are present in Uzbek.

According to V.N. Komissarov, the following grammatical changes occur when translating from English into Uzbek:

1. Zero grammatical transformation: *John took Mary by the hand - Jon Maryamning qo'lidan ushlab oldi.*

2. Transformation of a simple sentence into a complex one: *I want you to speak English - Ingliz tilida gaplashishingizni istayman. She hates his behaving in this way - Uning bunday xatti-harakatlaridan nafratlanadi. I like watching her dance - Men uning raqsini tomosha qilishni yaxshi ko'raman.*

3. Combining two sentences into one: It is not possible to do the work in two days. *Nor is it necessary. - Ikki kun ichida ishni bajarish mumkin emas. Bu ham kerak emas. The only thing that worried me was our front door. It creaks like a bastard. - Meni tashvishga solgan narsa bizning old eshik edi. U juda yomon g'ichirlaydi.*

Traditional speech usage offers many grammatical substitutes⁴. For instance, the majority of scenarios use the same Uzbek form of sorry (*sizga xalaqit qilmadimmi, vaqtida javob berolmaganim uchun uzr, noqulaylik uchun uzr so'rayman*) and situations of use (*shaxsiy munosabatlar, ish xati, rasmiy munosabatlar*). However, when translated into English, this phrase can also have functional meanings like "sorry for the delay," "we must apologize for the delayed answer," and "excuse me."

When translating, the most acceptable option is to consider a structural change, or conversion, wherein a similar-yet-different form that can stand in for the original one is used in place of the non-equivalent grammatical form if it is not an independent part of speech.

Therefore, to translate a gerund into Uzbek, one uses either the verbal noun that is morphologically closest to it, the infinitive, or the gerund itself in Uzbek: *On acquiring new animals, one of the many problems that face you is the process of settling*

⁴ Muminov O., Turgunov R., Rashidova A., Alimova D., - Translation - Written translation - Pismenniy perevod. -T., 2008.

them in - Yangi hayvonlarni sotib olishda siz duch keladigan ko'plab muammolardan biri ularni joylashtirish jarayonidir. He agreed to selling them - U ularni sotishga rozi bo'ldi. After visiting several toy-shops, we managed to buy a teddybear - Bir nechta o'yinchoq do'konlariga tashrif buyurganimizdan so'ng, biz ayiq sotib olishga muvaffaq bo'ldik. Adverbs are often subject to a complicated conversion: *The tired speaker was silent - Charchagan notiq jim qoldi. He kept obstinate silence - U o'jarlik bilan sukut saqladi.* Another method of grammatical transformation is unfolding. It shows up in the division of lexical-grammatical units into parts, each of which contains a portion of the starting data. When necessary, deployment is employed to transform synthetic forms into analytical forms, depending on whether the context calls for it or the grammar rules of the target language in connection to this form: *He gave this watch to his mother - U bu soatni onasiga berdi. The waiter pushed him away - Ofitsiant uni itarib yubordi.*

Conclusion. Consequently, the requirement for grammatical modifications in translation is a result of the two languages' structural disparities. The secret to a good translation is the freedom to apply all the methods of such changes.

REFERENCES:

1. Koptilov V.V. Theory and practice of transfer. - K., 2003.
2. Arnold I.V. Fundamentals of linguistic research: Textbook. - M.: Higher School., 1991.
3. Kazakova T.A. Translation techniques. - St. Petersburg: Union, 2004.
4. Kalinina V.D. Translation theory and practice. - M.: RUDN, 2008.
5. E. Ochilov., Theory and practice of translation. - T., 2012
6. Gafurov I., Muminov O., Qambarov N., Translation theory. - T., 2012
7. Gafurov I. Introduction to the specialty of translation. - T., 2008.
8. Muminov O., Turgunov R., Rashidova A., Alimova D., - Translation - Written translation - Pismenniy perevod. –T., 2008.

